

1.0 Abstract

A Comparison of Multiple Testing Procedures for Controlling the False Discovery Rate Under Unequal Variances.

Multiple hypothesis testing is used to control the False Discovery Rate (FDR) in genomic studies. The FDR is the expected proportion of the number of false positives from all the rejected null hypotheses.

The most commonly used multiple testing procedures were given by Storey and Tibshirani (2003) [3] and Benjamini and Hochberg (1995) [2]. Storey's q-value is similar to p-value and is based on FDR rather than false positive rate. The q-value method uses the p-values obtained from permutation test for equality of two means. Li et al. (2017) [4] proposed a new method based on Bonferroni's approach and named it Bon-EV procedure. Neubert and Brunner (2007) [5] proposed a non-parametric method to address the Behrens-Fisher problem of unequal variances.

This study proposes an adjustment of Benjamini and Hochberg, Bon-EV, and Storey's q-value methods to control the FDR under the assumption of unequal variances. The adjusted procedures use the p-values obtained by using Neubert and Brunner non-parametric test. Monte Carlo method has been used to compare the above testing procedures for their ability to control FDR to its nominal level for populations with unequal variances.

2.0 Introduction

Multiple hypotheses testing requires the simultaneous testing of more than one hypothesis. In this test, I individually test each null hypothesis for every hypothesis.

In genome-wide studies, thousands of genes are tested for differential genes under two conditions. In genome-wide testing, the goal is to find differential genes. Therefore, using traditional p-value cutoff for α named as Bonferroni correction, provides too many genes to be significant. Hence this method is identified as too conservative that the method can eliminate the number of true discoveries.

Hedenfalk et al. (2001) [1] Examined breast-cancer tissues from patients with *BRCA1*-related cancer, patients with *BRCA2*-related cancer, and patients with sporadic cases of breast cancer to determine whether there are distinctive patterns of global gene expression in these three kinds of tumors. They computed a modified F statistic and used it to assign a p value to each gene. A p-value cutoff of 0.001 was used to find 51 genes of 3,226 that show differential gene expression. Using a threshold of 0.0001, they concluded that 9–11 genes are differentially expressed.

Several approaches have been proposed to reduce the number of significant genes and control the FDR that comes from a wide collection of literature. Here I have briefly discussed some major researches:

Benjamini and Hochberg (1995) [2] discussed about the Family-Wise Error Rate (FWER) and false discovery rate (FDR) the FWER was controlled in the classical sense by a conservative type I error rate control, regardless of the hypotheses tested. By controlling the FDR instead, the FWER was controlled in a weaker sense as well. Multiple errors could be minimized in many applications through this method. However, they only focused on the new approach that calls for controlling the FDR and demonstrated that it could be developed into a simple and powerful procedure. Thus, the estimated cost for the control of multiplicity is not large.

Storey and Tibshirani (2003) [3] proposed the q-value as an FDR-based measure of significance for genome-wide studies. The q-value of a particular feature in a genome-wide data set is the expected proportion of false positives incurred when calling that feature significant. All the features were taken with q-values \leq some threshold α to attain a FDR $\leq \alpha$. According to [3], a systematic use of q-values in genome-wide tests of significance provides a clear balance of false positives to true positive results and gives a standard measure of significance that can be universally interpreted. Their proposed methodology is easy to implement and interpret, and it is fully automated as compared to the original FDR methodology [3] which was found to be too conservative for genomics and result in a substantial loss of power.

A study by Li et al. (2017) [4] examined the stability of Benjamini-Hochberg (B-H) and Storey's q-value FDR controlling procedures commonly used in genetic and genomics data analysis. This paper presented a new multiple testing procedure called Bon-EV procedure, which is more stable, has more FDR control, and has more power than Storey's q-value procedure as well as more power than Benjamini-Hochberg. As a result, it is an attractive procedure for microarray and sequencing data analysis.

Another problem that can be encountered during testing is thousands of genes at once can come with unequal variances. To test the hypothesis of two independent samples with equal means and unequal variance, we face a problem. This problem is called Behrens-Fisher problem. When two sample data are taken from the same population that follows the normal distribution, however, both do not have the same variance then we use Welch's t-test. There have been many proposed solutions to this problem which I have discussed further in Chapter three. Among such solutions are parametric and non-parametric solutions. I shall look into both solution types in Chapters Four and Five. In this study, I have chosen Welch's t-test and Brunner-Munzel test to address the Behrens-Fisher problem.

Neubert and Brunner (2007) [5] have proposed a permutation test based on the studentized rank statistics for the non-parametric Behrens-Fisher problem. The proposed process considered the samples of unequal variances in presence of the equal means and worked on the ordered categorical data. For this study, they used the central limit theorem of [6], and their extended simulation study showed that this permutation test worked for normal, non-normal and discrete distributions.

In this study, I propose an adjustment of B-H, Bon-EV and Storey's q-value methods to control the FDR under the assumption of unequal variances. The adjusted methods will use the p-values obtained by using Neubert and Brunner non-parametric test and the Monte Carlo method will be used to compare the above testing procedures for their ability to control FDR to its nominal level for the population of unequal variances.

3 Monte Carlo Study

3.1 Simulations

For this study, I have simulated 1000 genes. For each gene, I generated two samples, one of size n_1 and one of size n_2 , from two normal distributions. Out of 1000 genes, a proportion of the genes are differential. I have used two proportions of differential genes, and several variance ratios. Non_diff and Diff in Table 1 denote the number of non-differential and differential genes respectively. For this study, σ_1^2 and σ_2^2 are the variances for sample 1 and sample 2 accordingly. In addition, μ_1 and μ_2 are means of the number of non-differential genes. Similarly, $\mu_{1,d}$ and $\mu_{2,d}$ are means for the number of differential genes. All simulations have been done using R. I have used Bon-EV package which includes BH, Storey's q-value and Bon-EV methods and q-value package. The combinations for the simulations can be found in the below table:

		Proportion of Differential Genes					
		0.05			0.15		
		Non_diff = 950 Diff = 50			Non_diff = 850 Diff = 150		
Variance Ratio $(\frac{\sigma_1^2}{\sigma_2^2})$	Non_diff Means	Sample Size (n_1, n_2)			Sample Size $((n_1, n_2))$		
	Diff Means	(10,6)	(6,10)	(8,8)	(10,6)	(6,10)	(8,8)
$\frac{2}{2} = 1$	μ_1, μ_2	14,14	14,14	14,14	14,14	14,14	14,14
	$\mu_{1,d}, \mu_{2,d}$	20,14	20,14	20,14	20,14	20,14	20,14
$\frac{3}{2} = 1.5$	μ_1, μ_2	14,14	14,14	14,14	14,14	14,14	14,14
	$\mu_{1,d}, \mu_{2,d}$	20,14	20,14	20,14	20,14	20,14	20,14
$\frac{2}{1} = 2$	μ_1, μ_2	14,14	14,14	14,14	14,14	14,14	14,14
	$\mu_{1,d}, \mu_{2,d}$	20,14	20,14	20,14	20,14	20,14	20,14
$\frac{1.5}{.5} = 3$	μ_1, μ_2	14,14	14,14	14,14	14,14	14,14	14,14
	$\mu_{1,d}, \mu_{2,d}$	20,14	20,14	20,14	20,14	20,14	20,14

Table 1: Combinations for Simulations

Steps of the simulations are described below:

Step 1: Randomly generate two samples from normal distribution with means μ_1, μ_2 ; standard deviations σ_1, σ_2 ; and sample sizes n_1, n_2 .

Step 2: Repeat $P*(1000)$ times with $\mu_1 = \mu_2$ to simulate $P*(1000)$ non-differential genes, where P is the proportion of differential genes.

Step 3: Repeat $(1-P)*(1000)$ times with $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$ to simulate $(1-P)*(1000)$ differential genes.

Step 4: Two sample tests - Welch's, permutation Welch's, BM, and permutation BM have been used to obtain p-values for all 1000 genes.

Step 5: The sorted p-values of these 1000 genes are used to obtain FDR, FNDR, proportion of rejected genes for FDR methods - B-H, Storey's q value, and Bon-EV.

Step 6: Steps 1 to 5 have been repeated for 500 times.

Step 7: Average FDR and FNDR proportions have been computed from these 500 values.

The R-code is given in Appendix I.

3.2 Results and Discussions

In this study, we have used Welch's t-test, permutation Welch's t-test, Brunner-Munzel test and permutation Brunner-Munzel test to compute the p-values. Using p-values from each of the four tests, we have estimated the FDR by Benjamini-Hochberg, Storey's q-value and Bon-EV procedures.

The following tables give the mean FDR and FNDR when the proportion of true differential genes is 0.05 and variance ratios are 1, 1.5, 2, and 3 respectively. Benjamini-Hochberg procedure, Storey's q-value and Bon-EV methods are denoted as BH, q-Value and Bon-EV. We have shown for three different scenarios of sample sizes that are $n_1 > n_2$, $n_1 < n_2$ and $n_1 = n_2$. Tables 2 to 7 is for 5% differential genes and Tables 8 to 13 is for 15% differential genes.

Tables 14 to 19 in appendix II give the proportion of rejected genes for different combinations of sample sizes, variance ratios, and differential genes.

Figures 3 through 14 in appendix II illustrate Tables 2 through 7 in graphical form.

Variance Ratio	Welch's			Permutation-Welch's			Brunner-Munzel			Permutation Brunner-Munzel		
	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BM-BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV
1	0.049	0.053	0.052	0.049	0.053	0.052	0.185	0.191	0.188	0.046	0.05	0.049
1.5	0.041	0.044	0.043	0.035	0.038	0.038	0.138	0.142	0.141	0.029	0.036	0.036
2	0.043	0.046	0.046	0.037	0.039	0.039	0.122	0.126	0.124	0.027	0.035	0.034
3	0.049	0.053	0.052	0.045	0.048	0.047	0.11	0.116	0.113	0.029	0.037	0.036

Table 2: Mean FDR when $n_1 > n_2$ for the proportion of true differential at 0.05

Variance Ratio	Welch's			Permutation-Welch's			Brunner-Munzel			Permutation Brunner-Munzel		
	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV
1	0.006	0.005	0.005	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.001	0	0	0.004	0.004	0.004
1.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3: Mean FNDR when $n_1 > n_2$ for the proportion of true differential at 0.05

As can be seen from Table 2, for variance ratio 1, the mean FDRs of all the p-value tests are very close to 0.05 that means all procedures have maintained the false positives at the nominal level of 0.05. When my first sample size is bigger than the second sample size, BH, Storey's q-value and Bon-EV methods provide the best FDRs using the Welch's test. In addition, FDR estimation using permutation Welch's is better than that of BM and permutation BM tests.

In Table 3, when variance ratios are 1.5, 2 and 3, the three methods using four different tests discover all the false positives. Whereas, when the variance ratio is 1, the FDR methods can not recognize approximately 0.4% to 0.6% of true positives.

Variance Ratio	Welch's			Permutation-Welch's			Brunner-Munzel			Permutation Brunner-Munzel		
	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV
1	0.047	0.047	0.047	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.048	0.049	0.049	0.06	0.061	0.061
1.5	0.053	0.053	0.053	0.055	0.055	0.055	0.055	0.055	0.055	0.067	0.068	0.068
2	0.048	0.049	0.048	0.057	0.058	0.057	0.058	0.058	0.058	0.072	0.072	0.072
3	0.054	0.055	0.054	0.063	0.063	0.063	0.064	0.064	0.064	0.077	0.077	0.077

Table 4: Mean FDR when $n_1 < n_2$ for the proportion of true differential at 0.05

Variance Ratio	Welch's			Permutation-Welch's			Brunner-Munzel			Permutation Brunner-Munzel		
	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV
1	0.006	0.005	0.006	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.004	0.004	0.004
1.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.006	0.006	0.006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.001	0.001	0.001
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 5: Mean FNDR when $n_1 < n_2$ for the proportion of true differential at 0.05

Table 4 contains the mean FDR when $n_1 = 6$, and $n_2 = 10$ for 5% differential genes. I notice that the mean FDRs increase with the increasing variance ratios. In that sense, my considered methods overestimate the mean FDR except for variance ratio 1. However, if I compare with all the p-value tests, Welch's and permutation Welch's test provide better FDRs for all FDR methods.

Table 5 shows, the FNDR using Welch's test gives comparatively higher values than others which means the FDR methods considering Welch's test cannot mark out the higher number of true differential genes that is 0.6%. However, all the FDR methods using any test have identified all the differential genes when my variance ratios are 1.5 and 3.

Variance Ratio	Welch's			Permutation-Welch's			Brunner-Munzel			Permutation Brunner-Munzel		
	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV
1	0.041	0.044	0.043	0.048	0.052	0.051	0.155	0.161	0.159	0.045	0.046	0.045
1.5	0.046	0.049	0.048	0.058	0.063	0.062	0.164	0.168	0.167	0.053	0.054	0.054
2	0.051	0.054	0.053	0.073	0.077	0.076	0.174	0.179	0.177	0.066	0.066	0.066
3	0.057	0.062	0.06	0.108	0.112	0.111	0.187	0.19	0.19	0.091	0.091	0.091

Table 6: Mean FDR when $n_1 = n_2$ for the proportion of true differential at 0.05

Variance Ratio	Welch's			Permutation-Welch's			Brunner-Munzel			Permutation Brunner-Munzel		
	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV
1	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.003	0.003	0.003
1.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 7: Mean FNDR when $n_1 = n_2$ for the proportion of true differential at 0.05

Table 6 is for equal sample sizes. BH, Storey's q-value and Bon-EV methods considering BM test overestimate the mean FDRs and rest of the tests estimate close to the expected false discoveries. However, when I take bigger variance ratios, the FDRs (except Welch's FDRs) are more than the nominal level of 0.05.

When I calculate the FNDR for variance ratio 1, Table 7 shows the percentage of undiscovered true differential genes fluctuates between 0.1 to 0.3. In addition, for the largest variance ratio, the Welch's and permutation Welch's test, BM and permutation BM test work in the same manner.

Variance Ratio	Welch's			Permutation-Welch's			Brunner-Munzel			Permutation Brunner-Munzel		
	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV
1	0.042	0.050	0.049	0.038	0.043	0.043	0.083	0.086	0.086	0.023	0.037	0.036
1.5	0.038	0.044	0.044	0.034	0.040	0.040	0.087	0.092	0.091	0.028	0.040	0.039
2	0.039	0.046	0.045	0.034	0.040	0.039	0.082	0.086	0.085	0.025	0.039	0.037
3	0.042	0.050	0.049	0.038	0.043	0.043	0.083	0.086	0.085	0.023	0.037	0.036

Table 8: Mean FDR when $n_1 > n_2$ for the proportion of true differential at 0.15

Variance Ratio	Welch's			Permutation-Welch's			Brunner-Munzel			Permutation Brunner-Munzel		
	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV
1	0.005	0.004	0.004	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
1.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.001	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 9: Mean FNDR when $n_1 > n_2$ for the proportion of true differential at 0.15

Table 8 and 9 show the output for mean FDR and FNDR at 15% differential genes when $n_1 = 10$ and $n_2 = 6$. These tables show similar FDR and FNDR estimation as I have seen in table 2 and 3 respectively.

Variance Ratio	Welch's			Permutation-Welch's			Brunner-Munzel			Permutation Brunner-Munzel		
	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV
1	0.043	0.051	0.050	0.043	0.052	0.051	0.107	0.114	0.113	0.042	0.051	0.050
1.5	0.05	0.059	0.058	0.063	0.074	0.073	0.131	0.141	0.14	0.069	0.071	0.071
2	0.057	0.065	0.064	0.085	0.095	0.094	0.148	0.158	0.157	0.093	0.094	0.094
3	0.057	0.066	0.065	0.119	0.128	0.126	0.162	0.167	0.166	0.123	0.123	0.123

Table 10: Mean FDR when $n_1 < n_2$ for the proportion of true differential at 0.15

Variance Ratio	Welch's			Permutation-Welch's			Brunner-Munzel			Permutation Brunner-Munzel		
	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV
1	0.006	0.004	0.004	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.004	0.003	0.004
1.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.004	0.003	0.003	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 11: Mean FNDR when $n_1 < n_2$ for the proportion of true differential at 0.15

Tables 10 and 11 are the mean FDR and at 15% differential genes when $n_1 = 6$ and $n_2 = 10$ and similar description to Table 4 and 5.

Variance Ratio	Welch's			Permutation-Welch's			Brunner-Munzel			Permutation Brunner-Munzel		
	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV
1	0.037	0.044	0.043	0.042	0.051	0.05	0.084	0.095	0.094	0.04	0.044	0.043
1.5	0.048	0.056	0.055	0.077	0.085	0.084	0.085	0.088	0.094	0.093	0.058	0.058
2	0.045	0.053	0.052	0.058	0.067	0.066	0.09	0.0999	0.098	0.051	0.051	0.051
3	0.047	0.055	0.055	0.078	0.078	0.086	0.086	0.087	0.093	0.092	0.058	0.058

Table 12: Mean FDR when $n_1 = n_2$ for the proportion of true differential at 0.15

Variance Ratio	Welch's			Permutation-Welch's			Brunner-Munzel			Permutation Brunner-Munzel		
	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV	BH	q-Value	Bon-EV
1	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002
1.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.001	0.001	0.001
3	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Table 13: Mean FNDR when $n_1 = n_2$ for the proportion of true differential at 0.15

Tables 12 and 13 are the mean FDR and FNDR at $n_1 = n_2 = 8$ at 15% differential genes. According to Table 12, the FDR methods for BM test regardless of any variance ratio overestimate the mean FDRs. On the other hand, Table 13 contains only three different FNDRs whereas variances 1.5 and 3 provide no undiscovered true differential genes in all cases.

4.0 Conclusion

After comparing all mean FDRs, we can say that the three FDR methods – B-H, q-value, and Bon-EV - are not very different from each other for the four tests used to compute p-values.

The study has found that when a larger sample has a bigger variance, the Permutation-Welch's and Permutation Brunner-Munzel tests have a decrease in FDR while the FDRs obtained from Brunner-Munzel test has an increase in FDR. The Welch's test has performed better in controlling FDR level at 0.05. Considering mean FNDRs, almost all the FDR methods are identical for different variance ratios except for variance ratio 1. For the proportion of rejection, there is no significant difference in different FDR methods using the p-value from different tests.

When a smaller sample has a larger variance, all tests show an increase in FDR. However, the mean FDR from Welch's test is closest to the nominal FDR level. For FNDR, methods using permutation Welch's and BM test shows the maximum undiscovered true differential genes. In addition, the smaller sample sizes with higher variances overestimate the proportion of rejected genes.

For equal sample sizes, FDR increases as the variance ratio increases. Permutation Welch's test does a better job when variances are equal. The Welch's test is close to the nominal FDR level followed by the Permutation Brunner-Munzel test. Whereas the Permutation-Welch's test has the lowest FNDR. For the proportion of rejected genes, with the increment of variance ratios, the proportion of rejections do not significantly increase.

Since our sample sizes are less than 10, the Brunner-Munzel test overestimates FDR in all combinations.

For all kind of sample sizes, the Brunner-Munzel test has the smallest Non-Discovery Rate (FNDR).

In conclusion, Welch's test performs better in controlling the False Discovery Rate to its nominal value irrespective of the FDR test used. Among the three FDR tests, Storey's q-value and Bon-EV do a better job in controlling FDR level.

This study provides a good exploratory tool for genome-wide studies to identify differential genes in the presence of unequal variances. For future study, I plan to extend these tests to non-normal distributions.

5.0 References

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